

Evaluation on the Effect of Dry Season Irrigation and Technologies Disseminated To Vegetable Crop Farmers Under ADP Zone (I) of Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study aim to evaluate the effect of dry season irrigation and technologies disseminated to vegetable crop farmers under ADP zone (I) of Katsina State. Nigeria has the potential area of land in which agricultural production and income generation were made, therefore; food production in Nigeria is almost entirely rainfed. The data for the study were collected from 150 dry season irrigation farmers with the aid of structured questionnaire and interviews schedules. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data. The result of the study shows that (79.39%) of the respondents were male and (46.4%) are married with adequate farming experience. The dominant variety of vegetables grown in their areas is spinach, tomatoes and onion. It's recommended that respondents should be encouraged by the extension personnel to participate several cooperative societies and engage much in modern vegetable farming, this could enable them to take advantage to access to credit, finance and technical efficiency.

Keywords: Effect, Dry season Irrigation, Vegetable crops, Technologies disseminated, Farmers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vegetable production is a major crops growing in agriculture at recent times. The awareness and interest to consume vegetables for good health is increasing both in developed, developing and under developed nations. According to (Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 2009), vegetables play a significant role in supplying the essential minerals, vitamins and fiber not present in large quantities in starchy staple foods but essential in other aspect of foods. Vegetables add flavors to meals. They are tasty, healthy and supply both proteins and carbohydrates. Ahmed et al., (2021) defined vegetable as the edible portion of an herbaceous annual or perennial crop which could either be served raw (green/fresh) or after a little cooking. Dry season vegetable production also called vegetable forcing in the production of vegetable outside the normal growing season using certain infrastructures such as green houses, irrigation, watering can, etc.

Africa's use of irrigation falls far below that of Asia and the rest of the world, and far below the continent's irrigation potential. Moreover, the rate of expansion has slowed significantly since 2000 (Svendsen et al., 2008). Between 2000 and 2003, the rate of expansion in irrigation was only about a third of the longer-term rate (0.5 percent), suggesting a slow rate of irrigation development. In Nigeria, federal government's intervention has been establishing several irrigation dams in specific areas where

vegetables and other crops can be cultivated. Some of these areas include; Jibia, Dusingma (Zobe) and Ajiwa dams in the Region. The establishment of the dams has made possible the cultivation of dry season vegetables and other crops such etc. Dry season vegetables cultivation goes a long way to complement the rain fed system that has been with the people since time immemorial. According to (Teklebrhan, 2020), farmers adopt the production of vegetables due to the changing food habits of people and the increasing awareness of individuals towards balanced diet and concept of nutritional security. Vegetables are essential to human health. For instance, tomato fruits contain lycopene, a valuable anti-cancer and anti-cardiovascular chemical. Carrots contain carotene (precursor of the essential vitamin A), and many fresh vegetables contain vitamin C. Eating plenty of fruits and vegetables may reduce the risk of contracting some diseases such as heart disease, high blood pressure, and cancer. Vegetables are valuable in maintaining the alkaline reserve of the body. According to (Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 2009) vegetables are a good source of income for both men and women farmers and offers opportunities for the disabled to earn a living. Vegetables have great export potentials and are good sources of foreign exchange earnings (Teklebrhan, 2020). The significance of vegetables makes the production an all season crops. However, its production is hindered in the developing economy because of the high dependence on rainfall. Hence, a majority of vegetable producers utilizes wetlands (usually called Fadama) - supplemented with a simple irrigation system to raise vegetables. Both Governments and development agencies promote income-generating projects as a way of encouraging growth through increased agricultural production. For instance, there are dry season vegetable producers under the Fadama scheme in all the state of the Federation. In fact, the production of vegetables during the dry seasons has been a source of employment and income to the farmers for decades. Hence, most of the farmers producing dry season vegetables embark on the use of small scale low-cost irrigation techniques. Vegetable production is one of the most important enterprises and production systems in Katsina State and Nigeria in general. Because vegetables are one of the important component of human diet and they can be easily cultivated on small areas. Whereas, the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended a daily vegetable intake of 200 g per person. However, since the cultivation of dry season irrigated vegetables, there are lots of differences in the quality of the plants produced regarding texture, coloration, length and size of leaves, durability, and taste and the quantity of vegetables produced. Also, dry season vegetable production is seen as a way of alleviating poverty among the rural dweller. The effects of dry season vegetable production have not significantly affected the livelihoods of the producers since most of the vegetables farmers are still impoverished. They reduced productivity might result from inadequate information on improved practices of production and poor postharvest management. It is also paramount to note that the production of improved vegetables requires information's and the adoption of some agricultural technologies.

Statement of the Problem

Vegetable production in Nigeria is characterized by the use of crude implements, non-availability of inputs, illiteracy, expensive and complex technologies (Ango et al., 2017). However, Vegetable crops production is constrained by inadequate infrastructure, agronomic and socio-economic variables. This manifest as reduced number of practicing vegetable farmers (Adams, 1988). To some extent, dry season vegetable farmers may or may not be aware of vegetable production technologies. The effectiveness of these technologies is imperative for adoption and consequently increased yield and income.

Knowledge: At the knowledge stage the farmer will receive information about the new package because farmers tend to adopt those agricultural packages that are compatible with their needs for agricultural techniques.

Persuasion: After the farmer became sufficiently familiar with the new agricultural knowledge, a stage of Persuasion starts. It comprises an analysis and mental evaluation of the available information on the package. If the results of the analysis are positive, the farmer will try it on a small scale, and then expand its application. On the other hand, if the results of the mental evaluation are negative, the farmer will reject the new package.

Decision Making: At this stage, which means an individual's choice to adopt or reject the new idea or new agricultural package. If the farmer has found that the technique is not useful, he/she will reject the new package disseminated and if the farmer acknowledge that the new technique is good at raising agricultural production, he/she will accept the new agricultural package.

Confirmation: At this stage of confirmation, knowing that the decision is not the end of the adoption process, an individual try to verify the choice he has made and obtain information whether it was a good decision.

Consequences: According to information obtained by the individual in the previous four stages in the individual phase consequences, he will make the decision whether to adopt the agricultural techniques for good or reject them.

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of dry season irrigation and technologies disseminated to vegetable crop farmers under ADP zone (i) and (ii) of Katsina State. While the specific objectives are to:

- i. Describe the socio-economic characteristics of the dry season vegetables crop farmers in the state.
- ii. Assess the effects of dry season irrigation on vegetable crop farmers in the state.
- iii. Examine the technologies disseminated to the dry season vegetables irrigation farmers.

Hypothesis of the Study

HO_i There is no significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of dry season vegetable farmers and the effect of dry season irrigation in the study area.

2. Theoretical Framework of the Study

Theory of transferring and disseminating information is a new innovative theory in which Agricultural information dissemination is done through two basic stages. The first one is the transfer and dissemination of agricultural innovation to farmers and the second one is to convince farmers to adopt these innovations on their farms (Tai, 2012). The process of transfer of agricultural innovation is persuading farmers to apply them on their farms and done agricultural extension who have practical experience in the dissemination of agricultural innovations and know how to deal with farmers sociologically. This is done through training courses in various areas of agricultural extension and communication. The process can be therefore defined as a transfer of innovation, integrating and interconnecting a series of sub-processes (Ann, 2013). According to him, the transfer processes include:

A transfer or delivery of new idea from the source to the target area, a process of localization or harmonization of package, which is intended to make the technical fit with the environmental conditions of the target area and the package is compatible with the prevailing agricultural systems in the region through a test and confirmatory tests of the technique in the target area (Rogers, 2003).

Independent Variable
Determine the rate of adoption

Figure i. Theoretical Framework, Diffusion of Innovation and its Attribute (Rogers, 2003).

3. METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

This study was conducted in Katsina State, Nigeria. Katsina state has 34 Local Government Areas. The state lies between latitude 12° 52’N and 13° 19’N and longitude 7° 16’E and 8° 43’E. The State covers about 9, 341 square miles (24, 192 km²) of land mass. Based on the projected 2006 Census 3.5% increments the Population of the state is 7, 831, 300 million people (NPC, 2007).

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Reconnaissance survey was conducted to ascertain the dry season irrigation farmers in the state. Based on the survey, multistage sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample size of the study.

In the first stage, Zone A was purposively selected for this study due to the high number of irrigation farmers in the zone. In the second stage, purposive selection of three Local Government Areas will be applied to obtain the LGAs out of all the Local Government Areas in the state ADP Zone due to the high concentration of dry season farmers in the area. The third stage involves a random sampling by balloting of three villages out of the selected LGAs in the state. The fourth stage will involve the proportionate selection of 15% dry season irrigation farmers from the selected villages, thus to arrive at the sample size.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1: Distribution of Respondents According to Age (n= 150)

Age (years)	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	S.D
25 – 35	30	20.0		
36 – 45	21	14.0		
46 – 55	53	35.3	57.61 years	18.18
56 – 65	40	26.6		
66 years and above	6	4.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results presented in Table 4.1 indicated that 35.3% of the respondents were within the age range of 46 – 55 years, 20.0% were within the age bracket of 25 - 35 years, 14% were within the ages of 36 – 45 years, 26.6% were within the ages of 56 – 65 years and 6% were within the age bracket of 66 years and above as shown in figure 4.1. In addition, the mean age of the respondents was 47.61 years.

Figure 4.1: Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Table 4.2: Distribution of Respondents According to their Sex (n= 150)

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	119	79.39
Female	31	20.6

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Result presented in Table 4.2 shows that majority (79.4%) of the respondents were males while few (20.6%) of them were females. Therefore, male farmers were capable of adopting new agricultural technologies than their female counterpart as shown in figure 4.2. This is because females are not fully engage in the production due to the household schedules.

Figure 4.2: Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Table 4.3: Distribution of Respondents According to Marital Status (n= 150)

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	102	68
Single	39	26
Widowed	9	6
Divorced	0	0.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The findings presented in Table 4.3 revealed that majority (68%) of the respondents were married, (26%) were single and only few (6%) of the respondents were widows. These findings imply that the majority of the respondents were married as shown in figure 4.3. This could be due to the religious and traditions of the people in the study area where marriage is encouraged and considered as a sign of responsibility.

Figure 4.3: Distribution of Respondents According to Marital Status

Table 4.4: Distribution of Respondents According to Technologies Disseminated by the Extension Agents (n=150)

Technologies	Frequency	Percentage
Pesticides	39	26.0
Herbicide	38	25.3
(Fertilizer) NPK	63	42.0
All of the above	10	6.7

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Result in Table 4.2 revealed that (42.0%) of the respondents were disseminated with fertilizer NPK, (26.0%) of the respondents received pesticide, (25.3%) of the respondents were disseminated with herbicide, and only few (6.7%) of the respondents were adopted all the technologies disseminated as shown in figure 4.4. This finding implies that majority of the respondents received fertilizer in the study area.

Figure 4.4: Technologies Disseminated by the Extension Agents

Table 4.7: Distribution of Respondents According to Farming Experience (n= 150)

Farming Experience (years)	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
1 – 5	29	19.3		
6 – 10	38	25.3		
11 – 15	34	22.7	24.4years	18.0
16 – 20	25	16.7		
21 years and above	24	16		

Source: *Field Survey, 2026*

As indicated in Table 4.7 reveal that 19.3% of the respondents had 1 - 5 years of farming experience, 25.3% of the respondents had a farming experience of 6 – 10 years, 22.7%, of the respondents had a farming experience of 11 – 15 years, 16.7% of the respondents had 16 – 20 years of farming experience and only few (16%) of the respondents had a farming experience of 21 years and above as shown in figure 4.5. The mean farming experience of the respondents was 24.4 years. This finding implies that the respondents had ample farming experience in term of adoption of agricultural technologies. These findings are in line with Mamuda *et al.* (2012), reported that years of farming experience determine the level of adoption of modern agricultural technologies disseminated to the vegetable farmers.

Figure 4.5: Distribution of Respondents According to Farming Experience

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the majority of the respondents were male and married, with considerable experience in vegetable farming activities within the study area. The study further revealed that socio-economic characteristics significantly influenced the adoption of agricultural technologies among dry-season irrigation vegetable farmers. Among the various technologies disseminated, fertilizer application emerged as the most widely adopted technology by the respondents. This indicates the importance of fertilizer use in enhancing vegetable production and improving farmers' productivity in the area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Extension personnel should intensify efforts to encourage vegetable farmers to actively participate in cooperative societies. Membership in such organizations can enhance farmers' access to credit facilities, agricultural inputs, improved technologies, and other support services.
2. Farmers should be encouraged to adopt modern vegetable farming practices and technologies to improve productivity, profitability, and overall farm efficiency.
3. Government agencies and relevant stakeholders should strengthen extension service delivery to ensure timely dissemination of improved agricultural technologies and technical knowledge to farmers.
4. Access to agricultural finance and input support should be improved to facilitate greater adoption of recommended technologies and enhance the technical efficiency of vegetable farmers in the study area.

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